

Figure. Sub-group analysis of changes in mean $\pm$ SEM TEG R-time (Panel A) and TEG α -Angle (Panel B) from baseline (hyperglycaemia, PG 15 mmol/l) to euglycaemia (PG 5 mmol/l) during a rapid (blue colour) and slow (red colour) plasma glucose decline. Abbreviations: PG, plasma glucose; TEG, thrombelastography; TEG R-time, rate of coagulation activation; TEG α -Angle, rate of clot formation. ns = $p \geq 0.05$, * = $p < 0.05$

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Coronary arteries assessment in asymptomatic high risk patients with type 1 diabetes using optical coherent tomography

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Background and aims: Data about the cardiovascular (CVD) risk of people with type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM) is lacking. Most of the CVD risk calculators were created for people with T2DM and simple non-invasive examinations like calcium score or carotid ultrasound are not part of guidelines. The aim of our study was to assess coronary arteries in high-risk T1DM patients by the use of optical coherent tomography (OCT) to estimate their real CVD risk.

Materials and methods: Sixty-two individuals with T1DM, duration of DM at least 10 years, age 30–67 years, without prior history of atherosclerotic CVD or target organ damage were examined by carotid ultrasound and calcium score over 7 months. Twelve subjects were recognized as high-risk defined as a calcium score above 400 and/or the presence of two or more plaques in carotids. Afterwards, those people were examined by coronary angiography and OCT. All subjects were characterized by STENO1 Risk Engine Calculator with mean STENO1 10-year risk score 25.7%. Seven out of twelve (58.3%) people were treated with low-, 2/12 (16.7%) with moderate- and only 1/12 (8.3%) by high-intensity statin therapy. We assessed quantitative (maximal diameter stenosis, minimal lumen area [MLA]) and qualitative (thin-cap fibroadenoma [TCFA], very high-risk plaque [defined as TCFA with MLA < 3.5 mm², lipid arch > 180° and macrophages], macrophage accumulation [Figure-C], presence of thrombus or cholesterol cleft) OCT parameters.

Results: Mean age was 64.5 $\pm$ 1.8 years, T1DM duration 36.1 $\pm$ 11.5 years, HbA1c 58.5 $\pm$ 8.8 mmol/mol and baseline LDL 2.3 $\pm$ 0.6 mmol/l. Mean calcium score was 950 $\pm$ 976 and mean number of carotid plaques was 2.8 $\pm$ 1.1. Coronary angiography showed obstructive coronary

artery disease in 5/12 (41.7%) people, one of them underwent percutaneous coronary intervention. TCFA was identified in 7/12 (58.3%) people [Figure-A] and very high-risk plaque was present in 4/12 (33.3%) people [B]. We saw intraluminal thrombus [D] and cholesterol crystal [E] in 3/12 (25%) people. Mean MLA at left anterior descending artery (LAD) was 3.18 mm². Pearson correlation coefficient revealed a strong correlation between OCT maximal diameter stenosis and calcium score at LAD ($r=0.75$, $p=0.005$). We observed no significant correlation between the number of plaques in carotids and TCFA at LAD.

Conclusion: Our study showed that people with T1DM without previous history or signs of CVD with high calcium score and carotid plaques had very severe OCT findings. We observed high-risk features like TCFA which is associated with a very high risk of plaque rupture and also a fatal CVD event. Therefore these people should be treated as very high-risk individuals.

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Automated insulin delivery systems and vascular reactivity in type 1 diabetes: a prospective study

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Background and aims: Mechanisms underlying the increased cardiovascular risk in type 1 diabetes (T1D) are not completely known. Hyperglycemia, hypoglycemia, and glucose variability could all favor the development of atherosclerosis in T1D. Hybrid artificial pancreas (HAP) considerably improves glucose control and variability. Patients shifting from usual care to HAP represent a unique setting to test the impact of improved glucose control on vascular health. The aim of the present study was to evaluate the relation between glucose metrics and endothelial function and to assess the impact of 3-months use of HAP in patients with T1D.

Materials and methods: In a prospective cohort study we enrolled patients with ≥ 3 -year T1D duration without macrovascular complications, regularly using continuous glucose monitoring (CGM), candidates to HAP. All enrolled subjects underwent ultrasound vascular assessment including flow mediated dilation (FMD), arterial stiffness, and intima-media thickness (IMT) before and after 3-month use of HAP. Time in range (TIR) 70–180 mg/dl, time above range (TAR) 181–250 mg/dl and >250 mg/dl, time below range (TBR) 69–54 mg/dl and <54 mg/dl, coefficient of variation (CV) as evaluated by CGM were recorded.